

Join the European Policymaker Network for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)

Powered by EU4Advice & CORENET

Why join?

- ✓ Stay ahead of EU policy developments
- ✓ Collaborate with peers across Europe
- ✓ Share challenges and solutions from your region
- ✓ Access best practices, training materials & legal resources
- ✓ Connect with SFSC producers, advisors, and EU projects

Are you a policymaker passionate about sustainable food systems?

Become part of a network of trusted policymakers and help shape future recommendations for resilient, local food systems across the EU!

Register now!

EU Network of Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) Advisors Join the network now

Are you supporting farmers
and producers to:

- 1 Sell directly to consumers?
- 2 Strengthen their position in the value chain?
- 3 Transition to a more sustainable and socially responsible production?

Now is your chance to join the first-ever European advisory network focused on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs).

This network is part of the Horizon Europe projects EU4Advice and COREnet.
Our aim: to enhance the sustainability, competitiveness, and visibility of SFSCs across Europe.

As a member, you will:

Connect with a wide community of SFSC experts and advisors	Access training materials, workshops, and knowledge-sharing sessions
Participate in networking and policy-shaping activities	Be listed in a public database as a trusted SFSC advisor

Register now by filling in the
questionnaire

Why join?

This is a voluntary, flexible opportunity to grow your impact, build valuable connections, and contribute to shaping the future of food systems in Europe